

THE ROLE OF WOMEN LABOUR FORCE PARTICIPATION IN INDIA

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Cite This Article: Dr. S. Palani & P. Kohila, "The Role of Women Labour Force Participation in India", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 3, Issue 2, Page Number 31-33, 2018.

Abstract:

Women workforce participation rate is very important in our country to develop their economy in different ways. In India, workforce participation rate of men is higher than the women in all sectors, because the women labor force participation is also low due to many reasons like lack of awareness about the workforce, financial problems, lack of education, child care, lack of self-security and others. Women workforce participation is low level, so their share in GDP of our country is also low. So, this paper focuses the role of women labour force participation in our country and this paper suggests government and other sectors encourage and provide the necessary facilities and security to women for increase workforce rate.

Key Words: Women Workforce Participation

Introduction:

In India, men labour force participation is more than the women because in general, the participation of men is more among them women in all sectors. In recent years, the women's are more interested and also motivated to participate in all sectors but some social and economic situations are the barrier to our workforce. Hence, the women's betterment is very critical in our country. Both rural and urban women participate in the workforce of India. Educated and uneducated women participate in different sectors like agriculture, industrial and service sectors. In case, the women participation in the economy is equal with men, to help to reduce family burden, to develop all sectors, improve growth and development of nation and rate of GDP will increase in India, but due to many reasons the participation is low. So this paper mainly analyzes the role of women education in economic development.

Statement of the Problem:

Women labor force participation is low due to many reasons like financial problems, family ties, lack of education, child care and household works. Personal security in society is also an important factor in the participation of women in the workforce. Women face many problems in the workplace like lack of appropriate infrastructure, lack of self-security and so on. Even though some women's are motivated to participate in the workforce but availability finance, infrastructure and institutional support for marketing their products are very limited. So in our country the contribution of women in GDP is very low when compared to men. In some sectors, women's are working more hours than men's but the salaries or wages are low levels to women compared to men, especially in agricultural and allied sectors. In their situation, the women workforce participation rate is decreased.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study about women workforce participation rate in rural and urban areas.
- ✓ To examine the number of female teachers per male teachers at different levels of education.

Review of Literature:

Many authors studied the women labor force participation in economic development. They pointed out that women labour force participation is not on par with their counterpart.

Sumit Mazumdar and Guruswamy (2006) study explain the problems and prospects of female labour force participation in Kerala. Remarkable changes in the cropping pattern had displaced the large volume of the women workforce from agriculture, especially in the rural areas, and the primary sector is no longer the most significant channel of employment. Manufacturing industries, both at the household level as well as other than it, was also largely stagnant. Economic activity among women has only increased in the tertiary sector. These had further led to the intensification of unemployment in the state, more so among the educated females. Large-scale emigration and outmigration from the state brought about prosperity to a certain extent, but has failed to provide the tenable solution to the problem of unemployment. Convergence of these factors has led to a declining trend in workforce participation among females, besides widening the gender gap in employment during the last decade. The trends in work participation are equally acute in the districts. All the northern Malabar districts have witnessed a fall in the work participation rate among females, whereas the southern districts have witnessed a marginal increase⁽¹⁾.

Cameron et al (2001) study analyses the education and labour market participation in Asia. Women's education increases labor market participation and provides better employment opportunities for women and

hence raises their incomes. This raises the status of women both in society and within the family. There are also positive externalities to such a process, including a reduction in fertility and population growth, improved health and life expectancy of children, reduced infant mortality, and a reduction in environmental degradation. The empirical results indicate that the determinants of women's labour force participation rates in Asia vary dramatically across countries. Tertiary education is found to have a large impact on participation in all countries except the most developed country, Korea, where women's education has the very little effect on participation⁽²⁾.

Glaura Vasques de Miranda (1997) study focuses on women's labour force participation in a developing society. In any society, female labor force participation is contingent on both cultural and economic conditions. During the process of dependent capitalist development, rising levels of unemployment and underemployment may be expected to occur simultaneously and to affect women's participation in the labor force more than men's. The analysis of labor force participation in 1970 by social class to explain the lower absorption of women in the wage labor although married women are less likely to work than single more schooling increases labor force participation of both married unmarried women. However, since the majority of Brazilian has less than four years of schooling, schooling may be said to female employment⁽³⁾.

Shirley Nuss (1985) et al study examines the empirical relationship of GNP as an indicator of economic development and the education of women. This study suggested that economic development has a positive effect on female education for many countries. Economic development is a weak predictor of the integration of females as third – level graduates in the important fields of engineering and agriculture. The findings suggest that economic development does not promise the full integration of women in decision making positions for national development⁽⁴⁾.

Methodology:

The data is collected from secondary sources like the National Sample Survey Office, Ministry of Human Resource Development and Census data. Annual Growth Rate (AGR) is computed for this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 4: The trend in Workforce Participation Rate

Year	Rural				Urban			
	Female	AGR (%)	Male	AGR (%)	Female	AGR (%)	Male	AGR (%)
2000-01	28.7	0	54.4	0	14	0	53.1	0
2001-02	31.4	9.41	54.6	0.36	13.9	-0.71	55.3	4.14
2002	28.1	-10.51	54.6	0	14	0.71	53.4	-3.43
2004-05	32.7	16.37	54.6	0	16.6	18.57	54.9	2.81
2005-06	31	-5.19	54.9	0.54	14.3	-13.85	54	-1.64
2007-08	28.9	-6.77	54.8	-0.18	13.8	-3.49	55.4	2.59
2009-10	26.1	-9.68	54.7	-0.18	13.8	0	54.3	-1.98
2011-12	24.8	-4.98	54.3	-0.73	14.7	6.52	54.6	0.55

Source: National Sample Survey Office

* Based on thin sample

This table 4 shows that the workforce participation rate of males and females in rural and urban areas. Workforce participation rate of males is more or less equal in both rural and urban areas. In 2000-2012 the annual growth rate of rural female workforce participation is negative except 2001-02 and 2004-05 because the annual growth rate is positive. The annual growth rate of rural male participation rate is negatively slow in the last three years. In urban female workforce participation rate is high level (18.57 per cent) in 2004-05 and low rate (0.71per cent) in 2002. In the annual growth of the urban male participation rate is changed year by year in both positive and negative way. This result indicates that men workforce participation is higher than the female workforce. Because the females need to participate in the awareness programme and abolish superstitions.

Table 5: Number of Female Teachers per 100 Males Teachers at Different Levels of Education

Year	Primary	AGR (%)	Upper Primary	AGR (%)	Secondary	AGR (%)	Senior Secondary	AGR (%)
2006	65	0	67	0	61	0	62	0
2007	66	1.53	65	-2.98	63	3.27	61	-1.61
2008	80	21.21	67	3.076	61	-3.17	58	-4.91
2009	73	-8.75	71	5.97	60	-1.63	60	3.44
2010	84	15.06	75	5.63	63	5	63	5
2011	76	-9.52	80	6.66	61	-3.17	65	3.17
2012	79	3.94	76	-5	66	11.47	66	1.53

Source: Educational Statistics at a Glance 2016, MHRD

This table 5 implies that the number of female teachers per 100 male teachers at different levels of educational institutions. In 2008, the annual growth rates of primary teachers have increased 21.21 percent and in the period between 2009 and 2011, the primary teachers level has negatively slope. The annual growth rate of upper primary teacher level is 6.66 per cent in 2011 and negative rate in 2007-2012. The annual growth rate of secondary teacher level is 11.47 per cent in 2012 and in the past years, the annual growth rate is negatively declined. In the senior secondary teacher, the level is very low. This shows that the male domination is over females in this field.

Conclusion:

Women labour force participation is very important in economic development because the participation of women will help in increasing the share of GDP in India. The government has to provide appropriate facilities to women, this will encourage them to develop their knowledge and decision making power. Women have to be encouraged to participate in the workforce, as that will develop the economy of their family and also our nation. Government's subsidy and the loan given to women for business and education must be increased. Proper security should also be given to women in society this will also motivate them to participate in the workforce in more number.

References:

1. Sumit Mazumdar and Guruswamy. M., "Female Labour Force Participation in Kerala: Problems and Prospects", Paper Presented at the Forthcoming Annual Meeting Program, Population Association of America, March-April 2006, California, pp. 1-26.
2. Lisa A. Cameron, Malcolm Dowling,J, and Christopher Worswick, "Education and Labor Market Participation of Women in Asia: Evidence from Five Countries", *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, (April 2001), Vol.49, No.3, pp. 459-477.
3. Glaura Vasques de Miranda, "Women's Labor Force Participation in a Developing Society: The Case of Brazil", *The University of Chicago Press Journals*, 1997, Vol.3, No.1, pp. 261-274.
4. Shirley Nuss and Lorraine Majka, "Economic Development and Education of the Female Population: A Cross-National Investigation", *Sociological Perspectives*, (July 1985), Vol.28, No.3, pp. 361-384.
5. National Sample Survey Office.
6. Educational Statistics 2016, Ministry of Human Resource Development.